

[Tectonics]

Supporting Information for

Sedimentological evidence for pre-Early Permian continental subduction in the Dabie Orogen, central-east China

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All other Supporting Information (Files uploaded separately) can be found online:

The following geochemical data used in the study are available at Zenodo via <https://zenodo.org/record/7697813#.ZAnrFSIrvDU>.

Supplemental Dataset 1 (Supplemental Material Table S1 All the test data.xlsx). This file contains original sheet data for sandstone framework petrography, heavy mineral assemblages, and U-Pb ages and trace element analyses of detrital zircon, rutile and apatite.

Introduction

The supporting information contains Text for stratigraphy description. Figure S1-S9 for Supplementary Figures.

Text S1. Stratigraphy description

This study focuses specifically on basins that span the Middle-Upper Triassic through to the Lower Jurassic. A detailed geological map with sampling positions is shown on [Figure S1 in Supporting Information S1](#). These formations are briefly summarized below.

The Early Mesozoic strata of the Yueshan Basin consist of the Middle-Upper Triassic Huangmaqing Formation, the Upper Triassic Lalijian Formation and the unconformably overlying Lower Jurassic Wuchang Formation. The Huangmaqing Formation is separated from the underlying Lower Triassic Biandanshan Formation carbonates by an angular unconformity. The Huangmaqing Formation is dominated by thick to massive beds of purple-red mudstone and siltstone with red-green mottling, with a maximum thickness of about 1600 meters ([Li & Ding, 1982](#)). These mudstone and siltstone beds show roots traces and carbonate nodules in their middle-upper horizons. Through the detailed analysis of biostratigraphy, lithofacies and sedimentary sequences of the Huangmaqing Formation, it is suggested that the formation is a generally coarsening-upward regressive delta system and deposited under hot-arid climate conditions ([Yue et al., 1999](#)). The Huangmaqing Formation formed in a low-energy, shallow-water environment, with periods of subaerial exposure. It is interpreted as a delta environment that formed during a marine regression during the early uplift of the Dabie orogenic belt. The stratigraphic age of the Huangmaqing Formation has been suggested to be Middle Triassic (Ladinian stage, 242-247 Ma) based on its fossil record ([Li & Ding, 1982](#)) and Middle-Upper Triassic stage by geochronological dates ([Wang et al., 2021](#); [this study](#)), although more accurate estimates of the depositional age are still required. The Lalijian Formation is a series of lacustrine facies coal-bearing deposits, containing Late Triassic insects and terrestrial plant fossils ([Guo, 1984](#); [Huang, 1984](#)). At the bottom of the Early Jurassic Wuchang Formation, there is a layer of conglomerate with a thickness of 0-0.3 meters, with clasts mainly of quartz and chert. The conglomerate also marks an unconformable contact with the underlying Triassic strata.

In the Nanjing Basin, the Huangshi Basin and Yueshan Basin exhibit similar sedimentary sequences and sedimentary facies. The Huangshi Basin strata include the Middle Triassic Puqi Formation, the Upper Triassic Jigongshan Formation and the Early Jurassic Wuchang Formation. The Jigongshan Formation is poorly exposed in the Huangshi region and is just 20 meters thick, and disconformably overlies the Middle Triassic Puqi Formation which is comprised of gray-black mudstone, siltstone and muddy siltstone, with fine-grained sandstone at the bottom and interbedded coal seams. In the Nanjing region, the succession is comprised of the late Middle Triassic to early Late Triassic Huangmaqing Formation ([Yue et al., 1999](#)), the Upper Triassic Fanjiatang Formation and the Early Jurassic Zhongshan Formation. The biostratigraphy of the Huangmaqing Formation was studied in detail by many Chinese scholars in the 1980s. Based on the paleontological assemblages there are two diverging opinions on the age of the group that have yet to be resolved – Ladinian stage of the Middle Triassic *versus* the Carnian stage of Upper Triassic ([Yue et al., 1999](#)). The age of all formations has been constrained based on published biostratigraphy and sparse geochronological dates. Some representative field photographs are shown in [Figure S2 in Supporting Information S1](#).

Figure S1. Detailed geological maps for the sampled basins: (A) Yueshan basin; (B) Nanjing basin; (C) Huangshi basin.

Figure S2. Field photographs. (A) Abundant calcareous nodules in purple-red siltstone of the Middle Triassic Huangmaqing Formation, Yueshan Basin. It implies a dry and hot paleoclimatic environment in the Middle Triassic and frequent fluctuations of the ancient water table. It likely represents deposition on a delta top, lower-river interdistributary or floodplain. (B) Siltstone of the Huangmaqing Formation with abundant vertical burrows, Yueshan Basin. There are some marine-brackish bivalves present. Bedding is horizontal, but no flaser or lenticular bedding is observed. The depositional environment is interpreted as estuarine or sand bar deposits at a delta front. (C) purple-red siltstone of the Middle Triassic Puqi Formation, Huangshi Basin, with sandstones with large-scale cross bedding. The bottom of the image is comprised of a fine gravel (2-3mm) lens, with bottom scouring and large trough and planar cross bedding developed at the base and small-scale cross bedding and climbing ripples seen in coarse siltstones at the top of the gravel bar. It is interpreted as a meandering stream point bar. (D) purple-red siltstone of the Middle Triassic Puqi Formation

exhibiting small tabular cross-lamination and ripple cross-lamination development, Huangshi Basin. It is interpreted as a levee or crevasse splay facies deposit. (E) purple-red siltstone of the Middle Triassic Huangmaqing Formation exhibiting convolute bedding and water-escape structures, Nanjing Basin. It suggests a rapid depositional setting at a delta front. (D) purple-red siltstone of the Middle Triassic Huangmaqing Formation exhibiting small climbing-ripple cross-lamination, Nanjing Basin.

Figure S3. Petrographic photomicrographs. (A) micaceous litho-quartzose sandstone, 21DB05; (B) litho-quartzose sandstone, 21HM09; (C) litho-quartzose sandstone, 21HM13; (D) quartzose sandstone with a higher content of plagioclase, 21DB12; (E) litho-quartzose sandstone, 21DB25; (F) litho-quartzose sandstone, 21DB26; (G) litho-quartzose sandstone, 21DB10; (H) micaceous litho-quartzose sandstone, 21DB06. Qm=monocrystalline quartz, Pl=plagioclase, Mus=muscovite, Lm = metamorphic fragments. In all thin sections the dominant lithic fragments are metamorphic fragments.

Figure S4. Youngest detrital zircon ages calculated for the Triassic samples in in this study and published sample (Li & Hu, 2022; Wang et al., 2009, 2021).

Figure S5. Zircon age vs Th/U ratio. See Supplemental Material Table S1 for possible metamorphic zircons. Only have 50 zircon grains have a Th/U ratio less than 0.1 which may indicate a metamorphic provenance (Wu, 2020).

Figure S6. Plot of C1 chondrite-normalised (Sun and McDonough, 1989) REE abundance patterns for zircons. They are very few (1-3%) of zircons with REE signatures typical of eclogite-facies zircon (no Eu anomalies, flat HREE spectrum) (Wu, 2020). The REE patterns are plotted for the eclogite-, granulite- and amphibolite-facies metamorphic zircon and the magmatic zircon REE signature for comparison (Rubatto, 2017).

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